

Assessment of determinant factors responsible for divorce among divorcees in rural areas of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed factors responsible for divorce among divorcees in rural areas of Ibadan by specifically focusing on sexual satisfaction, ethnicity/culture, and educational disparities. Divorce is related to marriage and family, and it has been used as an instrument to expose failure through marriage. In Nigeria, the high rate of divorce is mostly associated with urbanization and industrialization. The study employed a multi-stage sampling procedure using a well-structured and closed-ended questionnaire. Three out of six rural local government areas were randomly selected, representing 50%. 354 divorcees were randomly selected out of 3,064 divorce cases heard in the last 4 years using the Taro Yamane formula. The collected data were analysed through descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (chi square). The study revealed that more than half of the respondents admitted that sexual intercourse brings peace to their family, while 52% disagreed that ethnicity has to do with divorce. Therefore, sexual activities between the couple must be set as a priority, with respect for one another's as well as unique cultural beliefs, customs, and communication preferences.

Keywords: Divorce; Sexual satisfaction; Divorcee; Ethnicity; Educational disparities;

1. Introduction

Marriage is the union of a man and woman, involving social and legal dependence for the purpose of founding and maintaining a family (Thomas, 2011; Singer and Joseph, 2005). Divorce is related to marriage and family, and it has been used as an instrument to expose failure through marriage (Strong, DeVault, & Cohen, 2011). As societies shift from feudal to liberal and industrial societies, divorce possibilities and frequency increase (Albertini & Garriga, 2011). In Nigeria, the high rate of divorce are mostly associated to urbanization and industrialization, leading to a shift towards nuclear families with less involvement of members in marital conflict resolution. Childlessness or involuntary barrenness is also a factor contributing to marital instability and divorce in Nigerian contexts (Olamijuwon *et al.*, 2020). Socio-cultural and economic factors also contribute to divorce, with new cultural patterns, aspirations, and behavioral norms emerging. There are still many more factors responsible for divorce which include financial and emotional instability, insufficient sexual intercourse, childlessness, households' jobs, and migration, lack of independence, sexual satisfaction, ethnicity/culture and educational disparities. (Stykes & Guzzo, 2020).

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Sexual satisfaction is an emotional reaction to sexual behavior that impacts sexual health, the longevity of a marriage, and overall quality of life. It is essential for emotional, mental, and physical well-being, overall success in life, avoiding risky behaviors, and maintaining positive social connections. It also enhances women's productivity and maintains marital connections (Uzdil & Özgüç, 2024). Marriage stability and sexual fulfillment are closely connected and crucial for overall physical and mental well-being (Zegeye, Woldeamanuel, Negash, and Shibre, 2020). Starc, Enea, Racz, Palatin, Gabrovec, Dido, Dahmane and Rotim, (2022), reported in their research that access to comprehensive sexual education, awareness of associated risks, top-notch sexual health care, and environments that promote sexual well-being are essential for individuals and families. Undoubtedly, sexual satisfaction cannot be exonerated as tangible factor for divorce among reproductive age couples in rural area of Ibadan.

Divorce is also likely to be predicted by ethnicity as claimed in multiple studies. Uzdil & Özgüç (2024), revealed that patrilineal families are less likely to divorce than matrilineal families likewise Abu (1983) found that after marriage, spouses in Ghana's Akan tribe continue to live apart in their ancestral homes because spouses receive more support from their respective homes than from one another therefore, Akan women have the financial means to end relationships and marriages in which they are uncomfortable or uneasy.

The empirical results regarding the relationship between education and divorce are debatable; some studies find a positive correlation between divorce and educational attainment, while others find a negative one. According to studies by Lindsay, (2020), a woman's chance of a divorce increases with her level of education. Conversely, Gerdes, (2017) made the case that educated women are more likely to have higher paying employment since they possess some kind of talent. A number of these ladies help provide for the family's necessities, which greatly helps to keep the marriage strong. İnceoğlu and Porgalı Zayman's (2023) study looked at the connection between chronic disease-affected couples' marital satisfaction and adjustment. Michael, Michel, Timothy, and Vincent, (1995) revealed that chronic illnesses and physical or mental disorders in any of the spouses have been shown to have a negative impact on marriages and harm marital adjustment. Research on the impact of illnesses on marriages has demonstrated that physical illnesses in one spouse negatively impact the functioning of the family and the ability of the marriage to adjust. İnceoğlu & Porgalı Zayman, (2023) linked high levels of marital happiness to better physical and mental health in couples.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Divorce and its associated implications directly impact on individuals, society and the nation at large. Among other things, the effects of divorce may include child maltreatment, emotional and psychological stress, a decline in standard of living, and the severing of family relationships. (Alkhalwaldeh, & Alqatawneh 2022; Shayesteh-Parto, Hasanpoor-Azghady, Arefi, & Amiri-Farahani, 2023; Büyükköçeci, & Leopold, 2024) Divorce is viewed as an act of dishonour since family honour and reputation are so important. Religion shapes perceptions of divorce, leading some couples to believe that they have a moral duty to continue in miserable unions. Divorce is also hampered by traditional gender norms and expectations, particularly for women. The stigmatisation of divorce also stems from the cohesiveness and unity of the family, which makes it harder for spouses to get a divorce. Shayesteh-Parto *et al.*, (2023) affirmed that educational attainment is a critical factor influencing individuals' socio-economic status and life outcomes. However, in many societies, including Nigeria, disparities in educational attainment between spouses, sexual satisfaction and/or ethnicity poses significant challenges within marriages. Despite these indications, there is a lack of empirical research examining the specific relationship between identified determinant and divorce rates among couples in Ibadan. As such, this study determines factors responsible for divorce among couples in rural area of Ibadan with specifically focusing on sexual satisfaction, ethnicity/culture, and educational disparities.

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Study area

The research was carried in rural area of Ibadan. Ibadan came into existence in 1829 by group of warriors led by Lagelu as commander in chief while the principal inhabitants of the city are Yorubas, Lyold, et.al (1967). Ibadan comprises of eleven (11) Local Governments areas where five local governments are urban in nature and six can be classified as rural and/ or semi-urban in the less city. The study targeted divorced couples living or present in the area.

2.2. Sampling Techniques and Procedures

This study employed multi-stage sampling procedure. Firstly, the rural local government area (LGA) (6) were selected. Secondly, 3 out of 6 existing rural LGA representing 50% were randomly selected (Ona Ara, Oluyole and Egbeda). Thirdly, Taro Yamane (1967) formula of sample size determination for a known population was used on total number

of divorce cases heard in the last four years three thousand and sixty eight (3068 cases) which gives value of 354 divorcees.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \text{ Eqn. 3.20}$$

where n = Sample size, N = Target population, e = Percentage of error 5% 1= Constant value

2.3. Method of data collection and analyses

A well-structured close ended questionnaire was administered in the study area to elicit data from the respondents. The total number of three hundred and fifty four (354) questionnaires were distributed while two hundred and eighty one (281) were properly filled and was returned representing 79.38% of the questionnaire distributed.

The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistical tool (frequency count and percentage), while inferential statistical tool was also employed using Pearson chi square and Chi Square formula for rechecking and certainty.

3. Findings

3.1. Relationship between sexual intercourse and divorce

This section analysed the effects of sexual satisfaction, ethnicity/culture, and educational disparities on divorce rate among divorcee in rural area of Ibadan. The study was analysed using chi-square on data generated from questionnaires distributed in the placement area of the study.

Table 1 revealed that more than half of the respondents admits that sexual intercourse brings peace to their family most especially when sexually satisfied, both parties are of good behaviors though it is on rare occasions before demanded from one another. This is in line with Collado *et al.*, (2021) which observed that when marital partners fail to satisfy each other in a sexual encounter, occurring over a long period problems ensure. In contrast, Arpacioğlu *et al.*, (2023) said sexual satisfaction has been highlighted as a metaphorical barometer of relationship satisfaction, indicating that sexual satisfaction is vital in an intimate relationship, possibly even a make or break factor.

Table 1 Relationship between sexual intercourse and divorce

Factors of sexual intercourse on divorce	Sexual intercourse as a factor for divorce						Total	%
	SA	A	D	SD	U			
Whenever there was sexual intercourse there was always peace in the family	SA	20	28	24	7	0	79	28.1
	A	20	26	14	10	0	70	24.9
	D	24	26	6	3	0	0	20.0
	SD	20	24	3	6	0	105	18.9
	U	10	6	0	4	0	0	7.2
Total	94		110	47	30	0	281	100
My spouse comes out with good behavior whenever he/she was sexually satisfied.	SA	26	24	26	4	0	80	28.6
	A	24	30	18	5	0	77	27.4
	D	22	10	10	10	0	52	18.5
	SD	22	10	10	6	0	58	20.6
	U	10	10	10	4	0	14	4.9
Total	104		84	74	29	0	281	10
My spouse rarely demands of me sexually.	SA	26	28	20	0	0	74	26.4
	A	26	26	12	20	0	84	29.9
	D	16	28	10	12	0	66	23.4
	SD	20	12	20	16	0	50	17.8

	U	0	1	2	4	0	7	2.5
Total	88		95	64	52	0	281	100
There was no much satisfaction with the degree of sexual intercourse between my spouse and I	SA	20	26	20	10	0	76	27.0
	A	26	22	6	8	0	62	22.0
	D	16	22	26	21	0	85	30.0
	SD	12	12	22	6	0	52	18.5
	U	0	2	0	4	0	6	2.5
Total	74		84	74	49	0	281	100

3.2. Relationship between Ethnicity/Culture and Divorce

It is undoubtedly that there are a lot of different culture and ethnics in Nigeria which certainly hold a great influence on individual attitude and characters. Table 2 revealed that about half of the respondents felt unfulfilled having married a spouse from different ethnic group though more than 52% had contrary opinion. The larger number of the respondents are pleased with the ethnic they married from while about 60% of the respondents are happy and speak well of one another ethnic wise. This therefore, supports the research findings of Telatar, (2019) that, there is relationship between ethnicity or cultural differences and determinants of divorce. This may be respect and high impetus for cultural tradition.

Table 2 Relationship between Ethnicity/Culture and Divorce

Factors of ethnicity\culture on divorce		Effect of Ethnicity differences has on divorce					Total	%
I feel unfulfilled having married a spouse from different ethnic group.	SA	22	16	14	8	0	60	21.3
	A	26	20	10	17	0	73	25.9
	D	24	10	28	18	0	80	28.5
	SD	10	14	20	24	0	68	24.3
Total		82	60	72	67	0	281	100
Am satisfied and happy with my spouse ethnic group.	SA	16	14	18	12	0	70	24.9
	A	1	20	24	20	0	78	27.8
	D	3	2	24	24	12	65	23.1
	SD	8	0	18	28	10	64	22.8
	U	2	0	2	0	0	4	1.4
Total		53	36	86	84	22	281	100
My spouse is happy and speak well of my ethnic group	SA	25	20	18	16	0	79	28.1
	A	28	26	12	18	2	84	29.9
	D	24	16	20	6	0	66	23.5
	SD	19	18	12	3	0	52	18.5
Total		96	80	62	43	0	281	100
Our cultural practice or belief most times contradict and make it difficult to agree	SA	20	20	16	14	0	70	24.8
	A	20	24	10	14	0	68	24.2
	D	26	28	20	12	0	86	30.6

on objective	specifics	SD	20	20	11	6	0	59	20.4
Total			86	92	57	46	0	281	100

3.3. Relationship between Educational Disparity and Divorce

Table 3 revealed that about 2/3 of the respondents are satisfied and proud with educational level of their spouse while more than 60% disagreed that the level of their spouse education caused them chaos while attending social function. About half of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed that their educational disparity brings misunderstanding at home whereas, more than 50% of the divorcee in the study area disagreed that their spouse level of education despise them these are the indications that there is no correlate between educational disparities and determinants of divorced among spouses in Ibadan although most of the previous researchers reported contrary and concluded that educational level has significant impacts on divorce also, Price, (2018) reported that the effect of education on rate of divorce and proved to be significantly related. Though this study is contrary and this may be due to urbanisation and industrialisation that has occurred in Ibadan. It can be suggested that Ibadan has turned to be urban environs where educational disparities doesn't have effect anymore

Table 3 Relationship between Educational Disparity and Divorce

Factors of educational disparity on divorce		Educational disparity as a factor for divorce					Total	%
I was satisfied and proud with my spouse level of education	SA	112	12	6	14	0	144	51.2
	A	11	18	18	2	0	49	17.5
	D	24	8	12	8	2	54	19.2
	SD	30	0	2	2	0	34	12.1
Total		177	38	38	26	2	281	100
Our educational disparity limited us from attending social function together.	SA	68	12	0	4	0	84	30.0
	A	5	8	8	2	0	23	8.1
	D	104	16	28	16	2	166	59.1
	SD	0	2	2	4	0	8	2.8
Total		177	38	38	26	2	281	100
Our educational disparity always brings fight and misunderstandings at home	SA	104	4	0	4	0	112	39.9
	A	9	24	6	8	2	49	17.4
	D	4	8	30	8	0	50	17.8
	SD	60	2	2	6	0	70	24.9
Total		177	38	38	26	2	281	100
My spouse always despise me of my low level of education	SA	53	12	2	0	0	67	23.8
	A	40	12	2	4	2	60	21.4
	D	24	12	26	12	0	74	26.3
	SD	60	2	8	10	0	89	28.5
Total		177	38	38	26	2	281	100

3.4. Chi square test of Relationship between sexual satisfaction and Divorce

From table 4 the statistical significance of the acquired chi-square value ($X^2 = 9.792$) at a confidence level of 0.05 with 4 degrees of freedom (df). To determine this, we compared it to the crucial chi-square value (Tab X^2) corresponding to the stated confidence level and degrees of freedom. The chi-square value (Tab X^2) required for a confidence level of 0.05 and 4 degrees of freedom is 9.488. Given that the calculated chi-square value ($X^2 = 9.792$) exceeds the essential chi-square value (Tab $X^2 = 9.488$), we can infer that the outcome is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Put simply, the outcome demonstrates a statistically significant relationship between sexual pleasure and divorce rates among spouses in Ibadan Metropolis.

The result obtained in this study further showed that, there is significant relationship between sexual satisfaction and divorce and this is in line with Tan, Goh, Sharmilah, and Tan's (2020) which revealed that married couples who were sexually compatible tended to experience higher levels of satisfaction in their sexual relationships, resulting in increased marital satisfaction. The study also inclines the views of Bahrami, Hosseini, Griffiths & Alimoradi (2023) which indicated that the level of closeness in a marriage and the ability to engage in sexual activities were the most influential factors in determining one's overall pleasure with life.

On the contrary, a study conducted by Jafarbegloo, Momenyan, and Khaki (2019) among postmenopausal women found that sexual dysfunction had no significant impact on marital satisfaction in postmenopausal women. Postmenopausal women do not need to be concerned about marital difficulties caused by sexual dysfunction. Also, the study declines the views of Dada, Okorodudu & Onoyase (2023) that indicated that there was no significant correlation between satisfaction and marital stability. The study suggests that secondary school counsellors should offer guidance on enhancing sexual activity abilities and marital relationships, particularly during pre-marriage consultations, to promote marital stability among married teachers.

Table 4 Chi square table of Relationship between sexual satisfaction and Divorce

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.792 ^a	4	0.100
Likelihood Ratio	8.404	4	0.078
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.949	1	0.047
N of Valid Cases	281		

$X^2 = 9.792$, Tab $X^2 = 9.488$ DF= 4 CONF. LEVEL = 0.05 = rejected and significant

3.5. Chi Square test relationship between Education disparity and Divorce

In the table 5 chi-square (X^2) value of 8.037 illustrates the research finding, which suggests that divorce and ethnicity are related. This association is compared to the critical chi-square value (Tab X^2) for a given degree of freedom (df) and confidence level (CONF. LEVEL) in order to assess its significance. In this instance, the crucial chi-square value at df = 3 and CONF. LEVEL = 0.05 is Tab $X^2 = 7.815$, but the computed chi-square value is $X^2 = 8.037$. At the 0.05 level of significance, we can infer that the link between divorce and ethnicity is statistically significant because the estimated chi-square value (8.037) is greater than the crucial chi-square value (7.815). This implies that, above what would be predicted by chance, there is a significant correlation between ethnicity and divorce among the group under study.

Practically speaking, this conclusion suggests that within the population under study, ethnicity may have an impact on divorce rates. The study corroborates the findings of Nukunya (1969), Nukunya (1992) and Abu (1983) which found that in Ghana which revealed that divorce also likely to be predicted by ethnicity; multiple studies support this claim. Research conducted in rural Nepal by Jennings noted that ethnicity was one reason why marriages failed. Either the patrilineal or matrilineal kinship structure, or both, constitutes the majority of ethnic groups. Research on family structures, especially in developing nations, has revealed that patrilineal families are less likely to divorce than matrilineal families.

Table 5 Chi square table of Relationship between Education disparity and Divorce

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.037 ^a	3	0.169
Likelihood Ratio	8.153	3	0.161
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.095	1	0.148
N of Valid Cases	281		

$X^2 = 8.037$, Tab $X^2 = 7.815$ df= 3 CONF. LEVEL = 0.05

3.6. Chi Square test of relationship between Ethnicity and Divorce

Table 6 indicates that the chi-square (X^2) value of 4.180 supports the research finding that there is no statistically significant relationship between divorce and education inequality. This relationship is compared to the critical chi-square value (Tab X^2) for a given degree of freedom (df) and confidence level (CONF. LEVEL) in order to assess its significance. In this instance, the crucial chi-square value for df = 3 and CONF. LEVEL = 0.05 is Tab $X^2 = 7.815$, but the calculated chi-square value is $X^2 = 4.180$. The null hypothesis was rejected since the computed chi-square value (4.180) is smaller than the crucial chi-square value (7.815). Consequently, at the 0.05 level of significance, there is not enough data to draw the conclusion that there is a statistically significant correlation between education difference and divorce.

Practically speaking, this conclusion implies that within the group under study, education disparity may not be a major factor determining divorce rates. The finding declines the study Tuchinsky, (2016); White (1990) and “Working-class Males and Engagement with High School Education,” (2015). Tuchinsky, (2016) observed that a woman's chance of a divorce increases with her level of education. Conversely, White (1990) made the case that educated women are more likely to have higher paying employment since they possess some kind of talent. A number of these ladies help provide for the family's necessities, which greatly helps to keep the marriage strong. According to “Working-class Males and Engagement with High School Education,” (2015) literature, education has a detrimental effect on the stability of marriages. Males with college degrees or higher have lower divorce rates than males with only a high school diploma or less.

Table 6 Chi square table of Relationship between Ethnicity and Divorce

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig
Pearson Chi-Square	4.180 ^a	3	0.243
Likelihood Ratio	4.188	3	0.242
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.097	1	0.756
N of Valid Cases	281		

$X^2 = 4.180$, Tab $X^2 = 7.815$ df= 3 CONF. LEVEL = 0.05

4. Conclusions

The study reveals a link between sexual satisfaction in Ibadan Metropolis marriages and divorce rates. Couples with higher satisfaction are less likely to divorce compared to those with lower satisfaction. This highlights the importance of addressing sexual gratification in marriage counseling and therapy. Incorporating sexual health and happiness into public health campaigns can improve relationships and reduce divorce rates. Providing information on sexual satisfaction and treatment options can lead to better marriage outcomes.

Additionally, the study's findings show a significant relationship between divorce rates and ethnicity. Therefore, encouraging cultural diversity and understanding can aid in lessening prejudice, stigma, and misconceptions about marriage and ethnicity. Campaigns for education and awareness can encourage communication, empathy, and respect between people of different ethnic backgrounds. Partners and their families must be cognizant of cultural differences and the particular dynamics and difficulties that exist within various ethnic communities. Respect for one another's unique cultural beliefs, customs, and communication preferences can improve the efficacy of marital stability. Couples of mixed ethnicity may encounter particular difficulties and experiences pertaining to cultural disparities and personal

identity. Strengthening connections and fostering marital stability can be achieved by offering resources and support that are specifically designed to meet the requirements of mixed-ethnic couples.

Conversely, the study found no evidence of a significant relation between divorce rates and differences in education. Furthermore, the analysis shows that there is no meaningful relationship between educational disparities and divorce rates. Furthermore, there was no significant correlation between the divorce and the spouse's health state. The lack of a substantial correlation between divorce rates and health status may indicate that married couples are resilient in the face of health difficulties. Therefore, it is necessary to concentrate on other characteristics such as income, employment status, communication patterns, and relationship satisfaction in order to have a deeper understanding of the causes that lead to divorce. The social and economic benefits of lowering dropout rates, increasing educational attainment, and improving access to high-quality education can extend to married stability.

Further Studies

Longitudinal studies and qualitative research approaches can offer more profound understanding of the dynamics of marital relationships and contribute to focused interventions aimed at enhancing marital stability and satisfaction.

To fully comprehend the fundamental causes of this link and its consequences for people as individuals, families, and communities, more investigation and study may be necessary.

To investigate additional potential elements or subtleties that might influence the association between education and divorce, more investigation and analysis might be required.

It's crucial to remember that this result is limited to the study's data and context, and more investigation may be required to look at additional variables that might have an impact on the association between divorce and health status.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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